

Reasons for Migration: Pull Factors of Determinants towards Urban Ward from Rural Villages

ABSTRACT

The present study has conducted to find out the causes and consequences of pull factors of migration in Visakhapatnam District and Andhra Pradesh state. Accordingly, the researchers have considered two mandals as study area to draw the sample respondents for applying research questionnaire to find out the political factors of urban ward migration. An attempt has been made to analyze the causes of the political related factors such as better leadership opportunities, better opportunities for participation in community meetings, proper democratic approach, better opportunities for systematic approaches to problem solving, better opportunities for understanding community problems, better political status and political freedom are responsible for migration and their consequences from the point of view of the migrant respondents of the villages of Araku Valley Mandal and Paderu Mandal of Visakhapatnam District. The researchers have selected a snowball sampling design in the present research study. In this type of sampling, the migrant respondents are used to identify other persons who must qualify for inclusion in the sample respondents. The researchers have designed the interview schedules (research tools) to collect the information from the respondents of the migration. The researchers have visited field survey to collect data and analyzed the same with help of Microsoft excel programme and drawn the results and findings.

Key Words: Reasons for Migration, Pull Factors of Determinants and Urban Ward from Rural Villages.

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Introduction

As per the “Report of the Expert Committee on Tribal Health ‘Tribal Health in India’ Bridging the Gap and roadmap for the Future”, 104 million tribal people in India are largely concentrated in ten states and in the North-East. Almost 90% of the tribal population of the country lives in rural areas. There are 90 districts or 809 blocks with more than 50% tribal population and they account for nearly 45% of the Scheduled Tribe (ST) population in the country. In other words, almost 55% of the tribal population lives outside these 809 tribal majority blocks. The above report also states that as per Census, 2011 over two-thirds of the tribal population is working in the primary sector (as against 43% of the non-tribal population), and is heavily dependent on agriculture either as cultivators or as agricultural labourers. The tribal people are increasingly moving from being cultivators to agricultural labourers. A comparison between Census, 2001 and 2011 shows that the proportion of cultivators reduced by more than 10%, while the proportion of agricultural labourers increased by 9% among the ST population. It is estimated that, in the last decade, about 3.5 million tribal people have left agriculture and agriculture-related activities to enter the informal labour market. Displacement and enforced migration has also led to an increasing number of Scheduled Tribes working as contract labourers in the construction industry and domestic workers in major cities. Currently, one of every two tribal households relies on manual labour for survival. Constitutional provisions under Schedule – V provide safeguards against displacement of tribal population because of land acquisitions etc. The Governor of the State which has Scheduled Areas is empowered to prohibit or restrict transfer of land from tribal and regulate the allotment of land to members of the Scheduled Tribes in such cases. Government has also enacted several Laws which have specific provisions with regard to displacement, rehabilitation and resettlement of tribal people.

Rationale of the study

The main focus of the study is on the influence factors, like causes and consequences of urban ward migration with particular reference to tribal mandals of Visakhapatnam District of Andhra Pradesh state from the point of view of the Migrant Respondents. Keeping this in view, the researcher has found that the highest number of tribal people are moving or migrating from villages to cities and other states for their livelihood, education, and better employment opportunities. Then, the researcher has planned to conduct a research study on influence factors like pull factors of migration from rural villages.

Objectives of the Study

The researchers have aim to find out the reasons of migration in the tribal areas with following objectives:

- To study the Causes of Political Factors for migration from the viewpoint of migrant determinants of the Tribal Mandals of Visakhapatnam District.
- To study the Consequences of Political Factors for migration from the viewpoint of migrant determinants of the Tribal Mandals of Visakhapatnam District.

Research Questions of the Study

- What are Causes of Political Factors for migration from the viewpoint of migrant determinants of the Tribal Mandals of Visakhapatnam District?
- What are the Consequences of Political Factors for migration from the viewpoint of migrant determinants of the Tribal Mandals of Visakhapatnam District?

Methodology

Out of 43 Blocks in the Visakhapatnam District of Andhra Pradesh State, the researchers have selected 02 (two) Blocks namely, i) Araku Valley & ii) Paderu to conduct the present study.

Study Design of the Study

The main purpose of the study is not the testing of any hypothesis. Being descriptive study, its basic thrust is to gain familiarity and insight into influence factors of urban ward migration with particular reference to the Tribal Mandals of Visakhapatnam District from the viewpoint of the migrant respondents of urban ward migration with particular reference to two Tribal Mandals of Visakhapatnam District.

Sampling Design of the Study

The researchers have selected a snowball sampling design in the present research study. In this type of sampling, the migrant respondents are used to identify other persons who must qualify for inclusion in the sample respondents. It has been already mentioned the researcher has made use of a snowball sampling design for the selection of the sample respondents as the researcher has to select the respondents who had returned to their places of origin on a temporary or permanent basis.

Preparation of Interview Schedules & its Validation

The researchers have designed the interview schedule to collect the information from the respondents of the migration. The interview schedules consist of the following:

- The personal background of the migrant respondents.
- The causes and consequences political factors of migration with special reference to Tribal Mandals of Visakhapatnam District.

Pre-testing was done to ensure against difficulties of comprehension and ambiguities of questions. Responses were coded and a preliminary analysis was done to see whether the interview schedule would yield required data. The necessary changes were made in the interview schedule accordingly.

Data Collection

The researcher had sought prior permission from the respondents and taken written undertaking to willingness to participate in this data collection process. This approach was found to be very useful and practical, as the respondents were well-informed of the purpose of the study and well-assured of its confidential nature. It took almost about three hours to interview each respondent of the villages of Araku Valley and Paderu Blocks in Visakhapatnam District.

Data Interpretation

The empirical, descriptive, and analytical methods have been used to analyze the data. The researcher also has made use of simple statistical techniques in the analysis of the research data.

Political Factors of Urban Ward Migration from Rural Villages

From the perspective of the migrant respondents from the villages of Paderu Mandal and Araku Valley Mandal in Visakhapatnam District, an attempt has been made to analyze the causes and consequences of the politically oriented pull factors that cause migration. These factors include better leadership opportunities, better opportunities for participation in community meetings, proper democratic approach, better opportunities for systematic approaches to problem solving, better opportunities for understanding community problems, better political status and political freedom.

Opportunities for Leadership

The respondents were questioned about whether migration aided their leadership development and whether greater leadership opportunities in urban regions were the reason for migration. Table 1 presents the responses of the respondents.

Table 1: Better Opportunities for Leadership

Sl. No	Query	Mandal	Responses of the Respondents		
			Yes	No	To Some Extent
1.	Do you think that better opportunities for leadership in urban areas were the cause of migration?	Araku Valley	32 (21%)	82 (55%)	36 (24%)
		Paderu	81 (54%)	32 (21%)	37 (25%)
2.	Do you think that migration helped you to acquire leadership?	Araku Valley	83 (55%)	38 (25%)	29 (19%)
		Paderu	97 (65%)	31 (21%)	22 (15%)

Source: Primary Data

According to the responses, 21% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 54% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal stated that better opportunities for leadership in urban areas were the reason for migration. 55% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 21% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal stated that opportunities for leadership in urban areas were not the reason for migration. 24% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 25% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal stated that opportunities for leadership in urban areas were cause of migration to some extent.

According to the responses regarding impact of migration as opportunities for leadership, 55% of respondents from Araku Valley Mandal villages and 65% of respondents from Paderu Mandal villages stated that migration assisted them in gaining leadership skills. 25% of respondents from villages in Araku Valley Mandal and 21% of respondents from villages in Paderu Mandal stated that migration was not assisted them in gaining leadership skills. 19% of respondents from villages in Araku Valley Mandal and 15% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal stated that migration was some extent assisted them in gaining leadership.

Possibilities to attending in Community Meetings

The respondents were questioned about whether migration has facilitated their ability to engage in community meetings and whether greater opportunities for involvement in these gatherings in urban regions were the reason for migration. Table 2 presents the responses of the respondents.

Table 2: Possibilities to attending in Community Meetings

Sl. No	Query	Mandal	Responses of the Respondents		
			Yes	No	To Some Extent
1.	Do you think that a possibility to attending in community meetings in urban areas was the cause of migration?	Araku Valley	41 (27%)	78 (52%)	31 (21%)
		Paderu	78 (52%)	37 (25%)	35 (23%)
2.	Do you think that migration helped you to attending in community meetings?	Araku Valley	76 (51%)	34 (23%)	40 (27%)
		Paderu	73 (49%)	36 (24%)	41 (27%)

Source: Primary Data

Table-2 shows that 27% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 52% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal stated that possibilities for participation in

community meetings in urban areas were the reason for migration. 52% of respondents from villages in Araku Valley Mandal and 25% of respondents from villages in Paderu Mandal stated that possibilities for participation in community meetings in urban areas were not the reason for migration. 21% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 23% of respondents from villages in Paderu Mandal stated, migration was cause of greater possibilities for community meeting involvement in urban areas to some extent.

According to the responses regarding benefits of migration as potential for community meeting participation, 51% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 49% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal say that migration made it easier for them to participate in community meetings. 23% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 24% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal say that migration was not made it easier for them to participate in community meetings. 27% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 27% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal say that migration was some extent helps their ability to participate in community meetings.

Independent Approach in Urban Areas

The respondents were questioned on whether migration is result of independent approach in urban areas and whether migration aided in improvement of the independent approach. Table 3 presents the responses of the respondents.

Table 3: Independent Approach in Urban Areas

Sl. No	Query	Mandal	Responses of the Respondents		
			Yes	No	To Some Extent
1.	Do you think that independent approach in urban areas was the cause of migration?	Araku Valley	35 (23%)	82 (55%)	33 (22%)
		Paderu	76 (51%)	34 (23%)	40 (27%)
2.	Do you think that migration helped you to improve the independent approach?	Araku Valley	80 (53%)	38 (25%)	32 (21%)
		Paderu	75 (50%)	35 (23%)	40 (27%)

The responses of the migrant respondents regarding the reason for migration shows that 23% of the respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 51% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal stated that independent approach in an urban area was the reason for migration. 55% of respondents from villages in Araku Valley Mandal and 23% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal stated that independent approach in an urban area was not the reason for migration. While, 22% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and

27% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal stated that independent approach in an urban area was some extent responsible for migration.

According to the responses regarding the effects of migration as independent approach, 53% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 50% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal said that migration improved their independent approach. 25% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 23% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal said that migration was not improved their independent approach. 21% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 27% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal said that migration was some extent improved their democratic approach.

Greater Possibility of Using a Systematic Approach to Problem-Solving

The respondents were asked if migration aided in the development of a systematic approach to issue resolution and if the greater possibilities for such an approach in urban regions are the reason for migration. Table 4 presents the responses of the respondents.

Table 4: Possibility of Using a Systematic Approach to Problem-Solving

Sl. No	Query	Mandal	Responses of the Respondents		
			Yes	No	To Some Extent
1.	Do you think that possibility of use systematic approach to problem-solving in urban areas was the cause of migration?	Araku Valley	25 (17%)	95 (63%)	30 (20%)
		Paderu	75 (50%)	40 (27%)	35 (23%)
2.	Do you think that migration helped you to develop a systematic approach to problem-solving?	Araku Valley	82 (55%)	42 (28%)	26 (17%)
		Paderu	75 (50%)	34 (23%)	41 (27%)

Source: Primary Data

According to the responses, 17% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 50% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal stated that migration was caused by better opportunities for a systematic approach to problem-solving in urban areas. 63% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 27% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal stated that migration was not caused by better opportunities for a systematic approach to problem-solving in urban areas. 20% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 23% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal stated that migration was partially caused by potential for a methodical approach to problem-solving in urban areas.

Table-4 shows that 55% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 50% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal stated that migration aided them in developing a systematic approach to problem-solving, according to study participants' responses regarding the impact of migration as better opportunities for such an approach. 28% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 23% of the villages in Paderu Mandal stated that migration was not aided them in developing a systematic approach to problem-solving. Additionally, 17% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 27% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal stated that migration was some extent aided them in developing a methodical approach to problem-solving.

Greater Possibility of Gaining Knowledge of Community Issues

The respondents were questioned about whether migration aided their comprehension of community issues and whether more opportunities to comprehend those issues in urban regions were the reason for migration. Table 5 presents the responses of respondents.

Table 5: Greater Possibility of Gaining Knowledge of Community Issues

Sl. No	Query	Mandal	Responses of the Respondents		
			Yes	No	To Some Extent
1.	Do you think that possibility to gain knowledge of community issues in urban areas were the cause of migration?	Araku Valley	21 (14%)	94 (63%)	35 (23%)
		Paderu	90 (60%)	32 (21%)	28 (19%)
2.	Do you think that migration helped you to understand the community issues?	Araku Valley	81 (54%)	38 (25%)	31 (21%)
		Paderu	76 (51%)	41 (27%)	33 (22%)

Source: Primary Data

According to the responses, 14% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 60% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal stated that migration was caused by better opportunities for understanding the problems of the community in urban areas. However, 63 % of respondents from villages in Araku Valley Mandal and 21% of respondents from villages in Paderu Mandal stated that migration was not caused by better opportunities for understanding the problems of the community in urban areas. 23% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 19% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal stated that migration was partially caused by greater opportunities to comprehend community issues in urban areas.

Table-5 shows that 54% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 51% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal said that migration helped them understand the problems of the community, according to the responses regarding the impact of migration as better opportunities for understanding the problems of the community. 25% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 27% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal said that migration was not helped them understand the problems of the community. Additionally, 21% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 22% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal stated that migration was some extent improved their comprehension of the community issues.

Improved Political Standing

The question of whether migration is a result of or a result of their improved political standing in urban regions was posed to the respondents. Table 6 presents the replies of the respondents.

Table 6: Improved Political Standing

Sl. No	Query	Mandal	Responses of the Respondents		
			Yes	No	To Some Extent
1.	Do you think that improved political status in urban areas was the cause of migration?	Araku Valley	35 (23%)	79 (53%)	36 (24%)
		Paderu	86 (57%)	34 (23%)	30 (20%)
2.	Do you think that migration helped you to obtain better political status?	Araku Valley	72 (48%)	40 (27%)	38 (25%)
		Paderu	76 (51%)	39 (26%)	35 (23%)

Source: Primary Data

The answers regarding the reason for migration, which is improved political standing shows that 23% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 57% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal stated that migration is caused by improved political standing in an urban area. About 53% of respondents from villages in Araku Valley Mandal and 23% of respondents from villages in Paderu Mandal stated that migration is not caused by improved political standing in an urban area. 24% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 20% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal stated that migration is some extent caused by improved political standing in an urban area.

Regarding the impact of migration on their political standing, 48% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 51% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal stated that migration improved their political standing. Around 27% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 26% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal

stated that migration was not improved their political standing. Also, 25% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 23% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal stated that migration was to some extent.

Political Independence

The respondents were questioned about whether migration aided their attainment of political independence and whether urban political independence is the root cause of migration. Table 7 presents the responses of respondents.

Table 7: Political Freedom

Sl. No	Query	Mandal	Responses of the Respondents		
			Yes	No	To Some Extent
1.	Do you think that political independence in urban areas was the cause of migration?	Araku Valley	41 (27%)	82 (55%)	27 (18%)
		Paderu	84 (56%)	28 (19%)	38 (25%)
2.	Do you think that migration has helped you to attain political independence?	Araku Valley	92 (61%)	35 (23%)	23 (15%)
		Paderu	87 (58%)	45 (30%)	18 (12%)

Source: Primary Data

Table 7 shows regarding the cause of migration as political independence that 27% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 56% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal stated that migration is caused by political independence in urban areas. About 55% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 19% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal stated that migration is not caused by political independence in urban areas. Around 18% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 25% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal stated that migration is caused to some extent by political independence in urban areas.

Table 7 shows the responses on the impact of migration on political independence, about 61% of respondents from villages of Araku Valley Mandal and 58% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal stated that migration assisted them in gaining political independence. Around 23% of respondents from villages in Araku Valley Mandal and 30% of respondents from villages in Paderu Mandal stated that migration was not assisted them in gaining political independence. Also, 15% of respondents from villages in Araku Valley Mandal and 12% of respondents from villages of Paderu Mandal stated that migration was some extent aided them in achieving political independence.

Conclusion

The overall analysis has shown from the details relating to the causes of migration of pull factors of political causes for the majority of the respondents in Paderu Block are not the causes for the majority of the respondents in Araku Valley Block. However, the consequences of migration of pull factors of political causes for the majority of the respondents in Paderu and Araku Valley Blocks have helped the overall development of the migrants. The above inferences drawn as a conclusion have enabled the researcher to develop a new theory on migration.

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